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STYLISTIC ANALYSIS OF JOHN KEATS' 'ODE ON MELANCHOLY': EXPLORING PHONOLOGICAL, GRAPHOLOGICAL AND LEXICAL ELEMENTS

Corresponding & Author 1:	AHMAD FARID , MPhil Scholar, Department of English, University of Education Lahore, Pakistan, Email: ahmadfariduoetcl@gmail.com
Co-Author 2:	ZAMNA SARFRAZ , MPhil Scholar, Department of English, University of Education Lahore, Pakistan, Email: zamnasarfraz@gmail.com
Co-Author 3:	HAMNA AMIR , MPhil Scholar, Department of English, University of Education Lahore, Pakistan, Email: hamnaamir1812@gmail.com

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Abstract

"Ode on Melancholy" by John Keats is a masterpiece of Romantic poetry notable for its in-depth analysis of human emotions and the human problem. He is an English poet whose work greatly influenced the romantic poets of the 19th century. His work attracted the attention of many critics who approached his texts intending to analyze them. The current research is qualitative and exploratory in nature. The current study examines the ode from a stylistic perspective focusing on three levels: phonological, graphological, and lexical. Phonological analysis focuses on the study of human language sounds and how they function and pattern in a certain language or languages. This study analyzed phonological elements such as alliteration, assonance, consonance, personification, anaphora, apostrophe, and symbolism in the poem to reveal its acoustic effects. The graphological level focuses on the visual features of the language, such as punctuation. This study is intended to discover how the visual structure of the poem affects the reader's interpretation and emotional response by studying these components. The lexical level investigates how individual words and phrases are blended in various patterns in various language settings. This level is all about parts of speech, and it is supported by TagAnt software. This study provided a thorough investigation of these phonological, graphological, and lexical aspects and highlighted a new perspective on "Ode on Melancholy." It not only expanded our understanding of Keats' literary style but also shed light on the links between stylistic elements and the emotional impact of the poem.

Keywords: *Stylistic, Melancholy, Phonological, Graphological, Lexical*

Introduction

Style refers to how a writer employs language, including word selection, sentence structure, and poetic elements, to communicate his ideas to readers. The way it is interpreted depends on the writing style of the author. The style reflects the author's personality as well. Robert Frost's books can be identified by his style since he uses straightforward storytelling language while constructing profound philosophical ideas using various elements of nature. According to [Tariq \(2018\)](#), stylistic work examines and assesses deviation in a literary work, a text that does not comply with norms and models linguistic description. Stylistic analysis of any writing or content is far different from literary text as it is more concerned with facts and is mostly objective. Finding the words and sensations that a text has on us is the main objective of stylistic and textual analysis. It is the branch of linguistics that studies and interprets different texts from different levels of stylistics like phonological, graph logical, morphological, semantic, lexical, and pragmatic. The phonological level focuses on the study of sounds used in human language and how these sounds function and pattern in a particular language and languages. This level is more related to achieving the stylistic significance of the text through literary devices. The graphological level is concerned with the graphic aspects of the language. Generally, it is the study of language in print. It is related to the written medium in terms of paragraphing, spacing, capitalization, font style, and, most importantly, pronunciation. Morphological level is concerned with words, their formation, and their relationship. The morphological level in stylistic analysis explores how a writer has used particular words to make his writing unique. Semantic relates to the investigation of the meaning and interpretation of language choices and text elements. Lexical level studies how individual words and phrases are combined in

different patterns in different linguistic contexts. This level is dedicated to parts of speech. The word categories, called parts of speech, include verbs, nouns, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, prepositions, interjections, and conjunctions. The pragmatic Level is the study of invisible meaning in spoken or written language is known as pragmatics. It talks about how to spot a text's hidden meanings. It is context-based research that takes into account the texts linguistic, thematic, prior knowledge, and physical context. The analysis in this study is done at the phonological, graphological, and lexical levels. The aim is to analyze the style and structure of one of the famous poems of John Keats "Ode on Melancholy". John Keats was the most accomplished of the romantic poets of English and made significant contributions that were so inadequately appreciated and published during his lifetime that he was unable to savor his later recognition and praise. His poetry is a succinct, in-depth synopsis of a lengthy work that inventively makes use of linguistic resources to evoke the reader's intended reaction. He used linguistic tools to present his expertise clearly and competently. The Keatsean style is well-known from his time. Garrett Stewart emphasized in his paper "Keats and Language" that John Keats was a self-taught poet, medically trained, and an instinctive anatomist of language, ligaments, and fibers, and its muscular tensions and releases, rhythmic corridors of breath. He was also an expert in the genetics and divinely gifted mutations of poetic art. He used his pen more like a stethoscope, listening to the phonetic pulse of the diction through the script's listening ear. "Ode on Melancholy," one of Keats' five odes written in 1819, is often regarded as one of his finest poems. The poem initially appeared in the book "Lamia, Isabella, the Eve of St. Agnes, and Other Poems" in 1820. The poem is primarily about

coping with and avoiding major depression. The voice appears as a kind of counselor, warning against turning to alcohol or death for relief from depression. Instead, the speaker suggests that we accept our pain. Additionally, the poem makes a connection between joy and sadness. The poem asserts that because everything wonderful is doomed to pass away, all beauty is infused with a form of terrible melancholy. This study explores the style elements of John Keats's "Ode to Melancholy" to demonstrate how Keats purposefully uses stylistic devices to demonstrate that the author never moves away or gets separated from the work. An analysis of these stylistic devices and techniques reveals that Keats is successful in producing a certain emotional impact and tone that goes beyond the bounds of typical language expression.

Problem Statement

"Ode on Melancholy" is considered one of the best odes of John Keats. Undoubtedly, this ode has received a lot of attention for its literary merits and thematic content, but there hasn't been much focus on its stylistic elements. The current study attempts to achieve this by analyzing the stylistic components of this poetry. There are many levels of stylistic analysis but the current research is conducted on three levels of stylistic analysis of this poem: phonological, graphological, and lexical. Keats employed a variety of stylistic devices, including personification, alliteration, assonance, and symbolism, to convey the poem's main idea. This research will help in understanding the linguistic structure and the intended message of the poet.

Research Objectives

- i. To explore the poem's form and style
- ii. To examine the stylistic devices at the phonological, graphological, and lexical levels.
- iii. To explore the meaning of the poem by using different stylistic levels.

Research Questions

- i. What is the style and form of "Ode on Melancholy"?
- ii. What are the stylistic devices used related to the Phonological Level?
- iii. What are the stylistic devices employed relating to the Graphological Level?
- iv. What are the stylistic devices used related to the Lexical Level?
- v. How do these stylistic elements help in understanding the meaning of the poem?

Significance of Research

This study will focus on the stylistic analysis of "Ode on Melancholy" by John Keats at various stylistic levels. All stylistic elements in the ode will be examined on three levels by the researcher. It will also tell us how these stylistic devices will help in the construction of the meaning of the poem. The exploration of all the levels will help in the thorough understanding of the whole poem.

Delimitations

This study will only analyze the poem "Ode on Melancholy" by John Keats and this analysis will be limited to this single literary work. The primary focus will be on the three levels phonological, graphological, and lexical within the poem and this study will not extensively explore other thematic or stylistic expectations.

Literature Review

Linguistics is the foundation of stylistic analysis of literary language. The word "style" is used to describe several linguistic variations, such as the language of legal documents and religion, so the term can be misleading. [Thomas S. Kane](#) describes the style as a linguistic feature pattern that distinguishes one work from another in Writing Prose. It means the writer's subject-related ideas, qualities, and presentation of the information for a particular audience and purpose are all included in the style. Style therefore encompasses a whole study

because it represents the author's voice or tone. It is a discovery for both the reader and the author. According to Buffon, the man is the style. William Labove was the main resource person who first introduced the term "style" in the 1960s in the context of sociolinguistics. Style refers to the way a person acts, thinks, and behaves in a particular manner. Style is the particular way in which language is used. Generally, style is something that speaks about the personality of any person. A style is defined in sociolinguistics as a collection of socially specific linguistic forms. The word "social" refers to a person's personality, group affiliation, views, values, and traits. [Leech \(1969\)](#) claims that style determines the structure, pattern, and placement of words in sentences in both written and spoken language. Charles Bally is considered the father of stylistics. He suggested this concept as a separate academic field to go along with Saussurian linguistics. Russian formalism serves as the origin of stylistics. In all spoken and written forms of communication, stylistics is the study of how language and tone are employed by different persons in various contexts. It is a subfield of applied linguistics. Stylistics verifies our viewpoint and increases our appreciation of literature due to its objectivity, linguistic insights, and practical principles. No serious student can escape stylistics now that it is interwoven with modern critique. Because of this, literary critics don't always agree with one another. Separate literary theory from stylistic research. invention of circumstances the writer's intent, and the moral assessment that follows, cannot be completely distinct from the means and fine texture that make up the style. The language and arrangements in a picture meld with literary patterns ([Carter & Stockwell 2008: 44](#)). Stylistics is the study of literary language through linguistic analysis. 'Style' was historically used to refer to other types of language, such as the

language of religion or legal documents, thus it can be confusing. Both of these types now go by the name registrations. The phrases "style" and "stylistics" refer to the very limited, specific application of linguistics to literature. Literary Language often veers off course. [Abbas et al. \(2020\)](#) researched the ode on the Grecian Urn penned by John Keats concerning stylistic analysis. The stylistic analysis of verse has been made on three levels: phonological level, grammatical level, and lexical level. John Keats was a worshipper of beauty. [Al-Erjan, \(2022\)](#) researched Ode to Psyche (1819) by John Keats. John Keats is a bard belonging to the Romantic era in the history of English literature. This research study examines "Ode to Psyche (1819) from a stylistic perspective. This stylistic analysis of Ode to Psyche reveals that John Keats is questioning the modern school of thought, which perceives that writers do not have any association with their texts. [Khan et al. \(2015\)](#) executed a research study on "To Autumn" by John Keats concerning stylistic analysis. This research study aims to explore "To Autumn" in terms of style and structure concerning the writer's description of nature and eternal life's beauty. In literature, style is generally defined as a mirror reflection of a person's personality. [Hafsa Zia et al. \(2017\)](#) conducted a stylistic analysis of John Keats's Ode to Nightingale. His research reveals the phenomenal style of John Keats' poetry. The data utilized in this research study is taken from the poem "Ode to a Nightingale," and then the data is processed through different software for stylistic analysis. This research has analyzed "Ode to a Nightingale" concerning eight levels of statistics such as adjectives, nouns, the mythical illusion of Hellenism, hyphenated words, alliteration, assonances, and consonance. Keats' unusual writing is the product of experiences he went through at a young age, and he is eternal just because of his writing style. [Ruban, A. F., & Backiavathy, H. U. \(2016\)](#) researched Ted

Hughes' poetry language from a stylistic standpoint. It also aims to examine how effectively the two levels of stylistics—lexical and phonological—appear and serve their respective purposes. Alliteration, assonance, and consonance are all part of the phonological level analysis, just as hyperbole and oxymoron are part of the lexical level analysis. Robert Frost's selected poems were the subject of a stylistic analysis by [Khan, A. B., Summara, & Saddique \(2014\)](#), who concentrated on the semantic and phonological levels of language. Alliteration, consonance, and assonance are used to highlight the worth of words in the poetry, while metaphor, symbols, and imagery are used to demonstrate the poem's content. Robert Frost, a modern American poet, is known for his unique writing style and innovative features of language in poetry. Modern American poet Robert Frost is renowned for his distinctive writing style and creative use of words. His distinctive writing style, which blends straightforward language with narrative elements, enables him to express his sentiments, emotions, and thoughts to readers. Frost's writing style distinguishes one type of work from another and exhibits the author's viewpoints on a certain topic or object ([Latif, Aneeqa & Ajmal, Muhammad & Maqbool, Saira & Khan, D & Assistant, 2022](#)). The poem "To a Skylark" by P.B. Shelley is the subject of this essay's stylistic examination. To clarify the poems' meaning, the study carefully analyses them using linguistic techniques. The research looks at a variety of factors, including phonological, grammatical, syntactical, and linguistic patterns. The study aids in comprehending the Themes, reviews, and presentation of nature and beauty in P.B. Shelley's poetry, as well as its structure and style ([Shawa, W. \(2015\)](#)). Shakespeare produced 154 sonnets in total, and they are renowned for their astounding profundity and beauty. One of the most well-known of

these great literary works is Sonnet 18, which is. The first line of almost every book is "Shall I compare thee to a summer's day?" But as this research demonstrates, Sonnet 18 is much more than just its lovely poem. The research reveals the sonnet's use of archaic terms, which lends it a timeless and ancient feel ([Quackenbush, K. C., Quackenbush, D. A., Epe, P. K. C., & Epe, P. I. T. C. 2019](#)). [Batool et al. \(2016\)](#) employ stylistic techniques to analyze William Wordsworth's poem "Daffodils" to comprehend the poet's point about how nature can uplift a downcast spirit. The analysis focuses on the poem's location and figures of speech, evaluating how the poet's social and cultural background informs the use of nature in the poem and how figurative speech strengthens its impact on the reader's mind ([Batool, Z., Kiran, S., & Azhar, M. A. 2016](#)). The study of linguistic texts known as stylistics focuses on literary criticism, critical discourse analysis, socialization, and meaning production. This essay examines the oral poetry subgenre "Ekun Iyawo," concentrating on the poetic devices and syntactic elements it employs. The analysis highlights the importance of "Ekun Iyawo" in Yoruba marriage ceremonies, emphasizing the need to uphold this tradition and appreciate the beauty of language ([Raji, O. W., & Ajadi, R. A. 2013](#)). The stylistic elements of "Stopping by Woods on a Snowy Evening" by Robert Frost are examined in this study. Little in-depth research has been done on Frost's use of stylistic devices, despite a lot of literature criticism research in that area. The research demonstrates that Frost employed several literary techniques, such as cacophony, alliteration, assonance, tone modulation, denotation, connotation, metaphor, personification, symbolism, and imagery to evoke a sense of horror and death. The study emphasizes Frost's description of human obligations and the short lifespan, which leads to despair and anxiety ([Hashmi, M. A., Mahmood, M. A., & Mahmood, M.](#)

I.2019). The poem "If" by Rudyard Kipling is examined phonologically, morphologically, and pragmatically in this essay. The poem's distinctive form and content—written as a fatherly piece of advice to Kipling's son—inspire discouraged youth and aid readers in comprehending the fundamental ideas of stylistics (Memon, M., Tunio, F., & Awan, M. 2021). Researchers use several levels of stylistic methods in the poem "Hope is the Thing with Feathers" by Emily Dickinson. Through a thorough analysis of the poem, this research reveals Dickenson's writing style, theme, personal beliefs, and attitude (Ali, H., Bhatti, I. A., & Shah, A. H. 2016). To comprehend punctuation, rhyme, alliteration, compounding, and semantics, this study uses stylistic analysis to analyze Thomas Hardy's poem "During Wind and Rain" and focuses on graph logical, phonological, morphological, and lexico-syntactical levels (Putri, A. 2018). The stylistic devices used in this article to analyze Blake's poem "Night" are graphological, syntactical, semantic, and phonological patterns. It aids comprehension of the poem's comparison of the present with a "New World" (Khan, A. B., Batool, S., Sandhu, M. A., Ahmed, M., & Batoo, S. 2014). A subfield of linguistics called stylistics looks at the formal aspects and purpose of writing. To highlight the concept of life, this study analyses Robert Frost's poem "The Door in the Dark" using the following stylistic devices: cacophony, alliteration, assonance, tone modulation, denotation, connotation, metaphor, personification, symbolism, and imagery (Handayani, M. R., & Abida, F.I.N. 2022).

Research Gap

As it is mentioned above, almost all the poems of John Keats have been used for stylistic analysis by different researchers except Ode on Melancholy. So this study will focus on exploring the stylistic devices of the poem at the phonological, graphological, and lexical levels.

Research Methodology

The current research is qualitative and exploratory. The researchers deeply examined and analyzed each word of John Keats' most famous poem "Ode on Melancholy" individually and in collocation concerning phonological, graphological, and lexical levels. In this study, we utilized TagAnt software as a tool for lexical analysis.

Analysis of the Poem

Phonological Level:

The poem "Ode on Melancholy" has three stanzas. In the poem, there are 10 lines in each stanza. Additionally, it is separated into a quatrain and a sestet. The poem has a strange rhyme pattern. Iambic pentameter was employed in the poem by the author.

Table I.

No.	Quatrain				Sestet					
Stanza-I	A	B	A	B	C	D	E	C	D	E
Stanza-II	A	B	A	B	C	D	E	C	D	E
Stanza-III	A	B	A	B	C	D	E	D	C	E

Here we find that the first four lines of the poem stand apart in terms of exact rhyme scheme while the final six lines do their things, too. There is variation in the last stanza in terms of rhyme scheme as compared to the first two stanzas. Although, it also starts with rhyme scheme A B A B the final six lines are different as compared to the first two stanzas. It ends with C D E D C E. It is similar to John Keats' famous ode "Ode on a Grecian Urn" because the last six lines' rhyme structure is also altered. The last stanza has its rhyme pattern since it is more philosophical than the first two, which are about how people react to melancholy. After reading this poem, we also discovered several significant poetic devices, including alliteration, assonance, consonance, personification, anaphora, and symbolism. Below is a discussion of these gadgets.

Alliteration

It comprises of the consonant sounds at the start of the word being repeated like:

- The repeated /s/ sound in "His soul salt taste the sadness of"
- The repeated /r/ sound in "Emprison her soft hand, and let her rave."

Assonance

It comprises poetry lines with words that use the same vowel sound repeatedly. Such as:

1. The sound of /ee/ in "And feed deep, deep upon her peerless eyes"
2. The sound /o/ in "Or on the wealth of globed peonies" and "A partner in your sorrow's mysteries"]

Consonance

It is made up of consonants that are repeated in a string of proximity syllables. For example:

1. The sounds of /th/ in "not the death-moth be"
2. The sound of /v/ in "in the very temple of Delight" and "No, no, go not to Lethe, neither twist."

Personification

It is a poetic device in which inanimate objects, such as plants or animals, are given human characteristics. Such as in the third and fourth lines of the first stanza, the nightshade is shown as having the human quality of a forehead kiss. Personification for melancholy is also employed in the 26th line.

Anaphora

The recurrence of any term or idea throughout the poem, such as: is meant.

1. "And feed deep, deep upon her"
2. "She dwells with Beauty—Beauty that must die,"

Apostrophe

Apostrophes are used to call people from a distance. The opening line of the poem refers to "melancholy."

Symbolism

Symbolism is the use of symbols to represent other ideas or concepts to convey a deeper meaning. For instance, "droop-headed flowers" and "Lethe, tight-rooted" are symbols of life and death respectively.

Graphological Level

There are three stanzas in this poem. If used, the poem's typical capitalization is obvious. Additionally, the poem makes use of a variety of punctuation. It focuses on analyzing the author's language use and how he uses various word choices to communicate his ideas. It describes a unique writing style that reflects the author's individuality.

Contraction

It is a technique that eliminates particular sounds or alphabets. Contraction is used in poetry to keep the lines' syllable count consistent. The poem uses contractions, for instance, "Kiss'd and Veil'd."

In a poem, contractions are employed to keep or reduce the amount of syllables in a line. This allows us to keep the meter as well. It helps in developing a poem's proper rhythm.

Semi-colon

A semicolon is used when linking or merging two or more independent clauses to make a sentence. In one sentence, it links two ideas and concepts. For Example:

Wolf's-bane, tight-rooted, for its poisonous wine;

Nor suffer thy pale forehead to be kiss'd

By nightshade, ruby grape of Proserpine;

Make not your rosary of yew-berries,

A semi-colon separates these two lines. The poet issues a warning in these lines regarding the threat posed by toxic plants and roots. He is claiming that all of them are intoxicants and that they all allude to suicide. Nightshade and wolf's-bane are dangerous plants. In these lines, he also gives the historical reference by talking about the "ruby grape of Proserpine". Proserpine or Proserpina is the Roman myth of the Greek Persephone

Coma

**But when the melancholy fit shall fall
 Sudden from heaven like a weeping cloud,
 That fosters the droop-headed flowers all,
 And hides the green hill in an April shroud;
 Then glut thy sorrow on a morning rose,**

The punctuation mark is used to create a pause in the speech. For Example: Commas are frequently used in poetry to indicate when the reader should pause. Commas were also used to fit a poem's flow. We use it occasionally to clear up confusion. By separating words with commas, it makes the concept clearer.

Lexical Level

The analysis of the poem showed that Keats used many parts of speech in the poem. We will see only nouns, pronouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs in the whole poem. For this level, Tag Ant Software is being used to prevent any ambiguity.

Table 2.
Analysis of Lexical Categories (Stanza#1)

Lines	Noun	Pronoun	Adjective	Verb	Adverb
Lines 1-10	Lethe	It's	Bane	Go	Tight
	Wolf	Thy	Rooted	Twist	Too
	Wine	Your	Poisonous	Suffer	Drowsily
	Forehead		Pale	Make	
	Kiss'd		Yew	Let	
	Night Shade		Mournful	Come	
	Ruby		Wakeful	Drown	
	Grape				
	Proserpine				
	Rosary				
	Berries				
	Beetle				
	Death				
	Moth				
	Psyche				
	Downy				
	Owl				
	Partner				
	Sorrow				
	Mysteries				
	Shade				

Table 3.
Analysis of Lexical Categories (Stanza#2)

Lines	Noun	Pronoun	Adjective	Verb	Adverb
Lines 11-20	Fit	Thy	Melancholy	Fall	Then
	Sudden	Her	Rich	Weeping	
	Heaven		Soft	Fosters	
	Cloud		Deep	Headed	
	Droop		Peerless	Hides	
	Flowers			Glut	
	Green			Rose	
	Hill			Globed	
	April			Let	
	Shroud			Feed	
	Sorrow				
	Morning				
	Rainbow				
	Salt				
	Sand				
	Wave				
	Wealth				
	Peonies				
	Mistress				
	Anger				
	Shows				

Table 4.
Analysis of Lexical Categories (Stanza#3)

Lines	Noun	Pronoun	Adjective	Verb	Adverb
Lines	Beauty	She	Adieu	Dwells	Ever
21-30	Joy	That	Very	Die	
	Hand	His	Sovran	Arching	
	Lips	Her	Strenuous	Turning	
	Bidding	Him	Cloudy	Seen	
	Pleasure			Save	
	Nigh			Burst	
	Poison			Taste	
	Bee			Hung	
	Mouth				
	Sips				
	Temple				
	Delight				
	Veil'd				
	Melancholy				
	Shrine				
	Though				
	None				
	Tongue				
	Grape				
	Palate				
	Fine				
	Soul				
	Shalt				
	Sadness				
	Might				
	Trophies				

The analysis of this level provides an in-depth understanding of the linguistic nuances within the poem. When the text is broken down into parts of speech using TagAnt software, the frequency of nouns stands out. This abundance of nouns indicates the poet's thoughtful choice to anchor the verses in concrete and tangible elements, strengthening the ode's rich imagery and significant emotional resonance. With an abundance of nouns, Keats skillfully uses language to evoke the indescribable and complex nuances of melancholy. By applying this lexical lens, Keats's skillful use of language to create an insightful examination of human emotion is demonstrated in the poem, which also becomes a literary masterpiece.

Findings and Discussion

This stylistic analysis reveals the remarkable aspects of John Keats' literary style, which helped to establish his immortality due to his heavenly ability to describe issues that are both thought-provoking and insightful with symmetrical dispositions. This analysis shows that there is symmetry at the phonological level due to the Ode's notable use of alliteration, rhyme scheme, assonance, and consonance. Personification and symbolism further enhanced the poem's beauty and charm, which was further embellished by the use of different punctuation marks like contraction, semi-colon, and coma. It is clear from the poem that nouns have a significant and widespread place in the linguistic setting. Their prominence provides a significant insight into the author's intentional stylistic decisions. As substantives, nouns are the fundamental building blocks of meaning communication, and their frequent use indicates a preference for clarity and striking imagery. The author gives the concepts and things covered in the poem a particular tangibility and solidity by using nouns as the main players. This conscious reliance on

nouns to create meaning points to an intentional stylistic decision, emphasizing their importance as the key elements around which the poem's themes and images are carefully built.

Conclusion

Every writer has a different style of writing that makes him unique in the world of writing. This paper inspects the poem "Ode on Melancholy" by John Keats who is a remarkable poet, he has his way of using words and arranging those words by using different techniques such as symbolism, imagery, personification, metaphor, and many other figures of speech to enhance the beauty of his writings. In this study, different levels of language and other stylistic features used in the poem are examined. He was adept at arranging sentences to fit the requirements of versification and showed a good awareness of how to use a variety of lexicons. The poem is undoubtedly a masterwork of language.

Limitations

The following are the limitations of the current study:

- Phonological, graphological, and lexical elements may be interpreted and perceived differently by different readers, resulting in differing conclusions.
- The influence of the historical and cultural background on the analysis is another limitation. Since "Ode on Melancholy" was written in the 19th century, it may be difficult to fully understand the nuances of Keats' stylistic choices due to the evolution of language and literary conventions over time.

Recommendations

Despite being done on three distinct linguistic levels—phonological, graphological, and lexical—the study's findings have wider implications focusing on the meaning, shape, and style of the poem as a whole. The study offers insightful understandings of the poem's overall composition by focusing on

these three levels, which in turn help in a deeper understanding of its more general thematic and stylistic components. This in-depth examination of phonological, graphological, and lexical features serves as a foundation for understanding the poem's complexities. The findings can help readers and scholars better understand how John Keats uses sound, visual presentation, and vocabulary to convey the melancholy theme, structure the poem, and craft its distinct style. As a result, this study serves as a stepping stone towards a more comprehensive understanding of "Ode on Melancholy" in terms of meaning, form, and style, and it may inspire further in-depth analysis to unearth additional layers of its literary richness.

Innovation/Research gap

This examination of John Keats' "Ode on Melancholy" provides a significant innovation as it thoroughly examines its stylistic elements at the phonological, graphological, and lexical levels. This study synthesizes insights from these various linguistic dimensions in a unique way. The poem's artistic expression can be understood holistically through the integration of phonological elements (alliteration, assonance, and consonance) with graphological features (punctuation, lexical patterns, and so on). This study not only broadens our comprehension of Keats' literary style but also enriches the academic discourse by providing these insights to scholars, educators, and enthusiasts.

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